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The Analysis of the Views of Turkish Pre-service Teachers on Classroom Management Based on Three Movies: *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)*, *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poets Society 1990*

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Abstract

Classroom management is a recurrent topic in the context of teacher education in online, face-to-face and hybrid educational context. The skills of classroom management are one of the most considerable issues of the pre-service teachers. Thus, the teacher educators should make them equip with the classroom management skills. This study focuses on the pre-service teachers' views on analyzing three movies as *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)*, *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poets Society* according to the freshmen and sophomore students' view at Faculty of Education in a compulsory course of 'Classroom Management'. The findings showed that 'lesson planning' is mostly identified ones. Moreover, it is clear that Mahmut, Luoanna and John all are role models for the pre-service teachers in terms of their attitudes towards the students and their profession. This study implies that the pre-service teachers need comprehensible and practical knowledge to model for themselves.

Keywords: Classroom Management, Teacher Education, Pre-Service Teachers

1. Introduction

Due to COVID-19, the teacher education has to be transferred into the online processes. The teacher educators have started to integrate more videos and online materials into their instructional process and the pre-service teachers have engaged with more in the online classes. This has brought the importance of the movies on education as the tools for training them. They are beneficial to comprehend the aspects and processes in the classroom environment such as the interaction types, the routines of the classroom and disruptive behaviors. There are numerous movies to be analyzed with the students. However, the teacher educators should decide which movie is proper for the purpose in the context of the needs and expectations of their teacher candidates.

The classroom environment is a social learning environment for the teacher candidates to understand the relationships, manners and behavior. Therefore, the pre-service teachers should be equipped with the necessary skills and techniques to facilitate this social environment. Also, it is a crucial component of pedagogical knowledge in teacher education (OECD, 2018). Classroom management is a proactive process and is defined as “*a well-planned set of procedures and routines for avoiding problems, and having a plan in place for when misbehavior does occur*” (Lester et. al., 2017:399).

In addition, classroom management is a construct for the effectiveness of learning process (Atilen et. al, 2017). According to OECD (2018), teachers spend 13% of lesson time to organize their own classrooms and they would like to have more professional support for managing the classroom. It is considered as one of the requirements for academic achievement and students’ engagement in addition to few behavioral problems (Marquez et.al, 2016). Lester and his colleagues (2017:410) stated “effective teachers *manage* their classrooms whereas ineffective teachers *discipline* their classrooms.” Therefore, teacher candidates should be acknowledged about the necessary skills for classroom management so as to be effective teachers (Egeberg, 2016).

Classroom management can be considered as one of the issues to challenge the pre-service teachers since they could not be aware of the ecology of the classrooms as well as other problems. The class is the minute social system including all the shareholders. In other words, the students, their parents, the school environment, the region and the educational policies either directly or indirectly manipulate the classroom social conditions and cause various challenges in the classroom. Unfortunately, the pre-service teachers have almost little about these factors and they have to cope with the disruptive problems though they are unprepared, as this is called as “reality shock” (Siwatu et.al, 2017; OECD, 2018). This makes them feel trapped, isolated or even alienated sometimes (Dayioğlu-Öcal, 2018). As a result, this signifies the importance of training pre-service teachers on classroom management. Furthermore, teacher’s self-efficacy is related to their classroom management skills (Atilen et. al., 2017; Kurt et. al., 2014, Bay, 2020). The higher self-efficacy level of the teachers is identified, the better classroom management skills are observed (Bay 2020, Siwatu et.al, 2017, Akkuş 2013). The self-efficacy of the pre-service teachers needs to be supported and empowered with different tools. (Aslan & Dayioğlu-Öcal, 2012, Dayioğlu-Öcal, 2018). McDonald & Hudder (2014) in their research, expressed a mentoring process in which Dan, as a novice teacher, and Joe, as a professor and mentor for him, collaborated together and solved the management problems Dan had come across. This experience sharing process obviously signifies that classroom can be a really dangerous environment for a teacher candidate if they have no skills to guide them appropriately (OECD, 2018).

Researches show that pre-service teachers face with more classroom management problems than experienced teachers (Siwatu et. al., 2017, McDonald & Hudder, 2014, Bayraktar & Doğan, 2017). This disrupts the instructional process and decreases the quality of the instructional time. Also, student engagement and student achievement in the classroom has strong relationship with the teacher’s classroom management skills (Flower et.al.,2016; Korkut, 2017). It is suggested that the teacher education programs should involve samples of misbehavior that the teachers could face with in the classroom. Brouwers and Tomic (2000) stated that teachers struggling with the classroom management problems could not conduct the instruction process properly so they are called as ineffective teachers. Selçuk and his colleagues (2018) found out that the competency of the teacher candidates differed according to the factors as gender, grade, time of the class hours and the field of the study.

In Turkish teacher education programs, all the teacher candidates are required to complete the pedagogical courses involved in their programs according to Council of Higher Education in Turkey. One of these courses specifically designed is ‘Classroom Management’. This two-hour course is conducted in the second or third semester according to the field of teacher education programs. It is theoretical and unfortunately the students have little chance to engage in the practice. This is one of the main criticisms emerged from this course. When the pre-service teachers face with the real ‘students’ and ‘classrooms’ at schools, they are more likely to feel insecure and worried (Korkut, 2017). Thus, the pre-service teachers should be more exposed to real-life situations rather than the demo lessons, simulations and role-plays. The only opportunity for the teacher candidates is ‘Practicum for Teaching’ in their fourth year and they are expected to demonstrate their management skills there. Of course, this cannot be considered enough. As a result of COVID-19, the course ‘Practicum for Teaching’ has to be done in the online classrooms in addition to face-to-face. Therefore, the students need to have more awareness of managing the online classrooms.

This study focuses on the movies on education the course and the students' analysis in the content of the course "Classroom Management", a compulsory course in teacher education program. The scope of this analysis is to find out the issues and aspects of 'classroom management' observed in three movies as *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)* 1975, *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poets Society*. The students were freshmen and sophomores at Faculty of Education enrolled in 'Classroom Management'.

2. Method

2.1 Research Questions

In this study, the main research questions are as below:

1. What are the problem field identified by the pre-service teachers in these movies?
2. How are the related constructs described by the pre-service teachers based on the movies?
3. What are the similarities and differences stated by the pre-service teachers related to classroom management in these movies?

2.2 Data Collection Procedure

In this study, the data collected from the pre-service teacher's term papers submitted for the course of 'Classroom Management'. Considering the challenges of employing the course 'Classroom Management' in the pandemic times, the researchers decided to analyze the project papers of the students on three movies as *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)* 1975, *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poets Society* to identify the classroom management constructs in the paper. These pre-service teachers are either freshmen or sophomore students at Faculty of Education in a state university in Turkey. The departments of the students were Foreign Language Education (English, German and French), Early Childhood Education, Elementary Education, Computer Education and Instructional Technology, Mathematics Education. In the requirement of the course, all the students were supposed to prepare an assignment to analyze three movies as *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)* 1975, *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poets Society* in pairs or in a group of 3-4. The total number of the term paper analyzed was 72 and the number of the students was 155.

The term paper assigned as one of the assessment component of "Classroom Management" course. The task involved analyzing three movies as movies as *The Chaos Class (Hababam Sinifi)* 1975, *Dangerous Mind* 1995 and *Dead Poets Society* 1990. The students were expected to identify *three main constructs as physical, humanistic, and instructional and lesson implementation and classroom interaction* in the classroom management. The assignment was required to consist of three parts as introduction, evaluation and conclusion. The first part focused on scrutinizing the topic and setting the context. The second part involved in the evaluation and the sample scenes and the transcription of that specific scenes and statements. The last part dealt with the general evaluation about the movies related to classroom management. These papers of the students on the task were collected from 2016 to 2020. The submission of was both online and the print-outs. The students prepared their papers in pairs and the group of 3-4. The students were informed about their assignments were to be used for the sake of the scientific researches by a consent form attached to their assignments.

2.3 Data Analysis

The content analysis was used in this study. In the first step, all the students' papers were analyzed by two researchers. The researchers identified the pre-determined key words such as "crowded classroom" and "time management". Then, they had a meeting to compare the key words identified and agreed upon them. The total of the codes identified by the researchers (N) was 741 and the codes they agreed upon were (n) 478. Thus, the interrater reliability was 0,64, which was considered as the moderate reliability level (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The distribution of all the codes identified according to the movies are shown in Table A1.

3. Results

The findings are constructed the concepts based on the research questions and in the literature. The concepts

emerged combined and listed under the titles of the themes as physical constructs, instructional constructs, human-based constructs, lesson planning, and misbehavior as in Table A2.

3.1 Physical Constructs

Physical constructs are basically considered as the setting of the classes regarding the content and course tools of the course. The readiness of the pre-service teachers is necessary before they get into the real classroom. In terms of this study, the sub-themes identified are ‘overloaded classrooms’ and ‘the large size of the classrooms’. The total student papers focused on this construct is 37 and the number of the construct referred most is 17.

The participants defined *The Chaos Class* with the adjectives of “overloaded, cold and noisy”. According to the findings, it is found out that “the number of the students in the classroom is 30 so the classrooms are crowded so the students’ personal area to be limited and to sit too close.” According to Başar (2014), the crowded classrooms are not efficient for the students to have a proper educational environment. One of the participants criticized the order of the classroom and stated that this leads to the problems of the classroom management as below:

In *The Chaos Class*, the traditional seating plan is a problem. This plan leads to a threat in classroom management. In *The Chaos Class*, one of the students, Necmi made a joke to Şaban, another student sitting in front of him by throwing a paper plane into his back. Also, in *Dead Poet Society*, the traditional seating plan is designed though the students sit individually. This can only be helpful only by arranging a space among the students so that there cannot be a problem.

Akin and his colleagues (2016) found out the similar case and highlighted the importance of the seating plan and how this impacts on the students’ misbehavior. In *Dangerous Minds*, the adjectives emerged are ‘spacious with big windows’, ‘dark’ and ‘noisy. This refers to the lightening and its effects on the students’. One of the participants expressed that ‘the darkness of the classroom environment caused the students behave ignorant and indifferent towards the content’. Also, *Dead Poet Society* is described as “traditional but appropriate for the teacher-student interaction” and “adequate lightening in the classroom”. It can be concluded that the awareness of the pre-service teachers impacts their skills in classroom management.

3.2 Instructional Constructs

In this study, instructional construct involves the themes as motivation (n=35), planning (n=23), evaluation (n=10), time management (n=7) and feedback (n=5). These are stated in two movies as *Dangerous Mind* and *Dead Poet Society*. Among these themes, motivation is mostly stated one among the all of them. In terms of motivation, a group of the participants commented on the manner of the teacher in *Dangerous Mind* by grading the students with the highest mark A and by expecting them to keep it as it is,

She (the teacher) expressed that she graded all of them the highest mark of “A” but the point was to keep the point as it was. This helps the students to get rid of the anxiety if grading. Also, she rewarded the students who can complete the assignments on time and are successful in the classroom.

Considering *Dead Poets Society* another group stated “the students started to learn the emotions and feelings behind the literary works instead of memorizing them and they had a view of art as a result of Keating’s literature course”. This statement indicates the power of the teacher on the students’ learning.

Compared to these two movies, the participants considered more problems in *The Chaos Class* than others due to lack of motivational aspect in the classroom. One group of the participants expressed that the students participated into the lessons just for making fun of the teachers and even teachers are not aware of them and they could not give understandable feedback to them. The group explained this as “lack of the repertoire of the teachers to motivate the students.” All the students in the class are repeats and have no care about the traditional ways of teaching. According to Akin et.al (2016), motivation is a necessity for the students to increase the engagement and the learned centeredness so this lacks in the students in *The Chaos Class*.

The planning is the secondary instructional construct stated by the participants. In *Dead Poet Society*, Mr. Keating had totally different planning and implementation of the lesson, which even caused a problem with the administrators and he lost his job. A group of the participants indicated Mr. Keating's extraordinary planning by exemplifying one of his statement from the movie: "Gentlemen, tell you what. Don't just tear off that page. Tear out entire introduction". This action makes the students amazed because Mr. Keating empathize their attitude towards the poem and act as they wish to do. This is an example of "instructional capacity of Mr. Keating" which directly impact on the attitude of the students; as a result, they start to build trust towards him in the learning process (Egeberg, 2016 & Lester et.al, 2017).

The participants identified *The Chaos Class* as the most challenging one in planning. One of the groups indicated that the teachers were usually reading the coursebooks, asking a student to present the content or writing the board the content and there was nothing to be considered as planning. Also, it is an indication that in the class the dominant teaching technique is lecturing rather than active involvement of the students.

The assessment part of the instructional process (n=10) is the other challenge identified by the participants. it is expressed that both teachers in both *Dangerous Minds* and *Dead Poets Society* have process-based evaluation; however, teachers in *The Chaos Class* have a product-based evaluation. One group of the participants stated:

We explored the case in *Dangerous Minds* where Mrs. Johnson asked some questions related to poems and evaluated their scores accordingly. Also, Mr. Keating asked the students to write their own poems for the evaluation. However, in *The Chaos Class*, evaluation is mostly associated with exams and they are used to threaten the students. The students are aware of this and they try to mock the teachers.

Therefore, *The Chaos Class* can be considered as the worst case compared to others.

Time management is another construct stated by the participants. Instructional process should be planned according to time allocation for each activity. The participants considered Mrs. Johnson's time management as the best in three movies. A group of the participants stated

Mrs. Johnson came to the classroom before the students to establish the environment. Also, as she realized that the students' attention had been low, she planned her lesson in advance. She never spends so long time for presentation and instructional part of the lesson but she focused on students' practice and reflection more.

In *Dead Poets Society*, one of the participants indicated that "the teacher could decide the time is enough when he could complete the tasks he formed in that specific learning objective." Thus, these movies confirm that ineffective classroom management inevitably causes to decrease time devoted to teaching and learning (Flower et al., 2016). Lester et al. (2017) focused on the effective time management by the teachers in the classroom to achieve their goals properly.

The last construct is feedback giving. In *The Chaos Class*, feedback giving was stated with "That's a great job!" and "Excellent" for the successful students. However, after these positive comments, the teachers went on the criticism on the others. In *Dead Poets Society*, Mr. Keating tried to encourage the participation of the students even if they answered the questions in a wrong way. In the scene which a student was reading a poem for his lover, other students started to laugh but Mr. Keating commented on "Your poem is a model one for the Romanticism; this is a great effort." In *Dangerous Minds*, Mrs. Johnson asked the students to identify the differences between the singer and the poet. She wanted them to find a poem by Dylan Thomas which was similar to Bob Dylan and she said this was a competition and she offered to have a dinner together as a reinforcement for their participation. In both *Dead Poets Society* and *Dangerous Minds*, feedback giving focuses on more encouragement and constructiveness whereas *The Chaos Class* deals with the teacher's criticism and despising manner towards the students.

3.3 Human-based Constructs

In this study, it is found out that human-based construct involves the themes as parental pressure (n=19), student personality (n=17), administrative pressure (n=16), parental ignorance (n=13), and teacher quality (n= 9). In line

with these, as it is seen, parental pressure is mostly stated construct among all of them.

In *Dangerous Minds*, parental pressure is mostly stated sub-theme and it is considered the most painful one. The participants of the study emphasized the scene in which one of the most intelligent students, Neil, is attending a medical school under his father pressure though he is interested in theatre. However, at the end, he committed a suicide. This showed that the parental pressure was a significant construct in this movie.

The student personality is the secondary human-based construct stated by the participants. One group of the participants compared three movies and they commented “Unlike to *The Chaos Class* and *Dangerous Minds*, the students in *Dead Poets Society* are successful students and draw good profiles as they are the children of authoritative and prestigious parents.” Moreover, some other participants classified the students as social and alienated both in *The Chaos Class* and *Dangerous Minds*, but successful, shadow and social in *Dead Poets Society*. According to most of the participants, the students in *The Chaos Class* draw the most spoiled profiles. A group of the participants stated “The students in *The Chaos Class* does not take the courses into consideration seriously. They have to be there so they focus on spending time. Ironic and shabby attitudes of students are main focus in the film.” This is highly related to their parental ignorant attitudes and manner towards these students as the director of the school in the movie stated in parents’ meeting at school (Akin et al., 2016).

The administrative pressure is the third human-based construct. In all three movies, a group of the participants stated as follows:

Being a teacher as a profession is emphasized in three movies. However, school administrators are authoritative, oppressive and focus on training one type of student. Furthermore, especially in *Dead Poets Society*, the school administrators and parents put some leverage on students for the same goals, but they do not deal with the abilities, needs and wishes of them, namely, disregard them.

This clearly indicates that authoritative, oppressive manner of the school administrators bring about aggressive and violent behavior among students.

In terms of parental ignorance, the participants commented on the manner of the parents in *The Chaos Class* by giving a dialogue sample:

Mahmut Teacher: What does your father do?

Necmi (Student): I do not know exactly, but he is probably a trafficker.

Principal: Most of the boarding students come from Anatolia, Mahmut teacher, and their parents get rid of them. They just pay the school tuition, then, they do not even call.

The participants explained that “education does not merely include the learning system, but also the integration of parents and school collaboration.” They also defined that the wall of the classroom is ‘transparent’, not physically but figuratively the classroom is open to the impacts from outside; especially from the students’ parents and the local circumstances.

Considering teacher quality, the participants explicitly defined *Mahmut*, *Louanne* and *John* as qualified teachers in their social and cultural context. The participant expressed:

Mahmut Teacher is a representative of the idealistic Turkish teachers. Louanne Johnson is a good negotiator who is rational, responsible, and acts by considering even the worst possibilities. John Keating is a literary and free spirited teacher. He has an innovative teaching style.

All these teachers are good at dealing with the misbehavior in the classrooms because they focused on not the student as the agent of the behavior but not the source of the problem. According to Atilen et.al (2016), misbehavior can be a result of the culture how the teachers react to them. They all react to the misbehaviors by focusing the reasons behind that rather than accusing them off the actions themselves. This also emphasizes the social skills of the teachers to deal with the misbehavior in the classroom (Korkut 2017).

However, some participants criticized the teacher quality in *The Chaos Class* as below:

The teachers in *The Chaos Class* use a traditional teaching approach, namely, their only goal is to teach something. They are incompetent for motivating and engaging the students. There are some teachers who go on teaching although they are older than their retirement age. They are not only old, but also nearly deaf or blind due to their ages. They insult the students with some nicknames as “donkey man, animal man”. In this film, all of these attitudes and their cultural implications should not be disregarded.

In terms of Turkish context in 1970s, the teacher authority is the main source of the classroom order and the students are passive and expected to obey the rules. This critic indicated the source of the teachers’ authority has changed into the source of the interaction with the students in current times. The belief that the senior teachers have better classroom management strategies is not valid according to the manners of the senior teachers in the movies (Karakaya and Tufan, 2018).

As a result, it can be obviously stated that three model teachers are deployed in these movies in the characterization of *Mahmut*, *Louanne* and *John*. They are represented as model teachers in their own contexts and communities. Though there are some administrative and parental challenges they have faced with, they always focused on how to solve the problems proactively rather than waiting for the solutions from the others and authorities (Akin et. al. 2016 & Girardet 2018).

3.4 Lesson Planning

In this study, lesson planning involves the themes as warming up (n=44), motivation (n=39), assessment and evaluation (n=16), presentation (n=3) and revision (n=3). Warming up is mostly stated one among all of them. One of the participants commented on the manner of the teacher in *Dangerous Minds* and expressed that she performed all stages of teaching in one lesson:

Ms. Johnson started the lesson by asking students whether they know how to do karate? By asking this question, she achieved the first step of lesson planning: warming up. She also stimulated wish to learn and interest on students, namely, motivation. Then, she started to teach verbs by using fill in the blanks technique and she mentioned that the most powerful verb is ‘to choose’ and people always have a ‘choice’. In this way, she completed presentation step. For the assessment and evaluation step, she gave homework in groups on finding similarities between legendary singer Bob Dylan and Poet Dylan.

Also, some participants gave John Keating’s manner as an example for the warm-up: “He was whistling when he entered into the classroom. Then, he attracted students’ attention on the issue by asking which poem include “O Captain, My Captain” verse.”

The participants commented that in *The Chaos Class*, there is little lesson planning. One participant expressed “it is seen that teachers have no worries such as warming up and motivation while teaching. Moreover, the students distract the focus of the teacher so the teacher cannot reach presentation step”. Thus, the lessons always end in chaos and they cannot achieve any objectives in the courses. Furthermore, in the same movie, the participants commented on assessment and evaluation step:

When it comes to assessment and evaluation stage, by claiming: “I cannot make an examination for three months. Whenever I attempt, I find myself over the shoulders”, the teacher declares that he cannot perform correction and feedback process of assessment and evaluation step.

In *Dangerous Minds* and *Death Poets Society*, it can be concluded that *Louanne* and *John* are better at lesson planning compared to the teachers in *The Chaos Class*. This planning is the main reason behind their achievement in these challenging classrooms. This finding supports the importance of lesson planning for the novice teachers to conduct the classroom management in the studies of Akin et.al (2016) and Lester et.al. (2017).

3.5 Interaction in Class

In terms of the study, the total student papers focused on this construct is 86 and the terms stated frequently under the heading of interaction in class are teacher-student (n=35) and student-student relationships (n=29). In terms of

teacher behaviors to create communication in class, meeting (n=14) and knowing students' name (n=8) is considered most by the participants. One participant commented on the theme by comparing three movies in terms of teacher-student and student-student relationships:

In *The Chaos Class*, the relationship between teacher-student on communication in class is weak although the relationship between student-student is high. *The Chaos Class* has a brotherhood connection, but they spread terror towards other students inside the school. They bully them and exclude them from their cliques. In the movie *Dangerous Minds*, in terms of classroom communication, both teacher-student and student-student relationship is poor. One group that cannot tolerate each other, and in even their own groups has lack of communication. Together with the fight and conflict stemmed from the lack of communication, the atmosphere is becoming tense and this causes the breaking the rules. During the process of becoming a class that listen each other and feel respect, great effort is observed to empower teacher-student communication. In *Dead Poets Society*, teacher-student relationship in class is at hierarchical level. The students do not reflect their problems to their teachers. The classroom rules and levels are clear and strict. However, together with Mr. Keating, this level softened and turned into a positive and extraordinary one. In terms of student-student relationships, it is seen that students' guards take care of them and they protect each other.

Some participants categorized student-student interaction level by comparing three movies. One of the participants stated "*The Chaos Class*, the interaction among students is nearly primary group interaction. They do not have any formality level and always make fun of each other" and exemplified the conversation as below:

One student: A cat does not enter into the classroom.

Another student: (Referring another student in class) A donkey can, why not a cat?

In *Dangerous Minds*, though students did not care about the teacher at first, the teacher achieved to attract their attention and interacted with them. In this interaction between two students, Emilio and Raul and Louanne transformed from secondary group into primary one. In *Dead Poets Society*, the communication among students is primary group interaction from the beginning. As they live in boarding school, they feel close to their friends rather than their parents; therefore, they support each other as it is seen in the scene where Neil shared his dream of being an actor and his friends supported him as stated by one of the participants.

In conclusion, in these three movies, what Mahmut, Louanne and John as teachers have achieved is their success to interact the students and able to get into their cliques, of course by getting their trust.

3.6 Misbehavior

The participants identified 172 actions which can be categorized in this group. When the sub-themes are regarded, the most identified one (n=70) is breaking the classroom and/or school rules. This includes making the noise (n=14) and breaking the flow of the lesson (n=14). The other three actions are disrespectful manners (n=10), cheating (n=6) and attending the class late (n=5). In all these three movies, the classes were depicted as noisy and chaotic by the participants. Regarding *The Chaos Class*, the participants identified this class as the most challenging one. One group of the participants mentioned: "The age level of the students is above 15. The developmental changes in students' learning are not considered. This caused some problems in the classroom management and the implementation of the course."

The participants identified some scenes as the critical ones with regard to breaking the classroom and/or school rules. They criticized the students' meeting in a secret place by leaving the school in *Dead Poets Society* as this would be risky. In *The Chaos Class*, the participants mentioned the students were smoking in various parts of the school and the dormitory. Additionally, some participants commented: "The students came to class late and they said "Sorry" but in a sarcastic way. This manner is to break the rule of attending on time."

The participants scrutinized that the students manipulated their teachers in the movies by making fun of their physical weaknesses and degrading the behavior. (n=29). In *The Chaos Class*, the pre-service teachers exemplified this by the scene as below:

Teacher: Hey, you, wearing glasses at the back! What are you talking about?
Student: (By chewing gum) Nothing, teacher.
Teacher: Then, tell me what I was talking about.
Student: You were talking about something.
Teacher: (Touching his ears) Pardon?
Student: The weather was getting hotter and hotter, teacher.
Teacher: Well done, sit down.

As it is seen in the dialogue, the students are making fun of the teacher's deafness and they are ignorant towards the lesson content. Moreover, in the analysis of *Dangerous Minds*, a group of the participants stated that when Louanne, the teacher, went into the class, the students called her as "white delight" to make fun of her existence and to show they were not caring her authority, all of which led the teacher to leave the classroom. One of the participants expressed the scene about the teacher's first entrance into the class as below:

When the teacher first entered the classroom, everybody in class was singing a song, dancing, and nobody was care about the teacher. Although the teacher kindly asked them to be quiet, the students behaved as if she did not say anything. When the teacher asked them about their previous teacher, they exclaimed such negative sentences as "She is asking the big butt, I started to love that slut, Emilio ate her".

In addition, mobbing (n=19) and physical violence towards the peers (n=7) are considered as the most frequent themes. The actions included are calling the peers with the nicknames, swearing, threatening and calling down. Regarding *The Chaos Class*, one of the participants indicated "students are kidding and calling each other with nicknames which despise them"; e.g. Grind Şaban, a name of the student in the class. In *Dangerous Minds*, the participants stated:

Two students were fighting and Louanne, the teacher, tried to separate them by interfering the stronger student and told him to stop fighting due to his overpower. This caused more problems because in order to survive in that community, they had to fight better. Therefore, the intervention of Louanne was not a solution for this case but caused more problem between the students as she was not sensitive enough towards the cultural settings behind their fight.

The participants focused on that the teachers should act in a culturally sensitive way (Siwatu 2017). The teacher should know the values, i.e. the physical power, regarded in the context. In other cases, the teachers' interference cannot be accepted and taken into granted and even this can cause another fight outside the school.

The participants also explained all these misbehaviors started to decrease in *Dead Poets Society* and *Dangerous Minds* since John and Louanne drew the attention of the students to the content through their lesson planning. These movies supported the findings of the study conducted by Sanetti et. al (2018) that "the implementation of evidence-based classroom management strategies decreases the disruptive behavior of the students" (p. 57).

4. Conclusion and Discussion

The findings of this study are crucial for teacher educators as the online materials were considered more important during COVID-19. These materials should be designed to raise the awareness of the pre-service teachers towards the real-life classroom environments. The movies on education has become one of the main resources for the evidence-based classroom management training (Marquez et.al. 2016, Flower et. al. 2016 & Sanetti et. al. 2018). The analysis of three movies indicated that the participants of this study elaborately criticized *Dangerous Minds* more compared to two others. This is because it may be the most recent one among them.

In addition, it is fully agreed by the participants that Mahmut, Luoanna and John all are model teachers, who care about their students' needs, expectation, experience and future. The self-efficacy levels of these teachers are so high that they could manage these difficult classes and the students by focusing on the real problems related to the family, school and the student. Thus, it can be said that these teachers focus on the preventive strategies of classroom management, which provides the background behind the misbehavior (Bayraktar & Doğan, 2017). Okutan (2015) stated that the untrustworthy and over- authoritative classes are the main barriers in learning. They

all have empathy with the students, are achievable by them and affectionate towards them.

This study contributes into the field of teacher education on proposing movie on education as a tool for improving the classroom management skills of the pre-service teachers (Marquez et.al. 2016). The movies will raise their awareness on these skills and give them an opportunity of applying into the context (Girardet 2018, OECD 2018). Improving classroom management is essential for the pre-service teachers before they start professional life. The more secure they feel in terms of classroom management, the more confidence they can have and the better learning environment they can provide. Therefore, integrating the movies on education into the content of teacher education programs will be helpful during post-COVID-19.

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Appendix A

Table A1: Distribution of the Frequency of the Constructs According to the Movies

Constructs	Hababam Class	Dangerous Minds	Death Poets Society	TOTAL
Physical Constructs	86	35	30	151
Instructional Constructs	15	137	122	274
Human-based Constructs	107	120	76	303
Lesson Planning	10	125	92	227
Communication in Class	46	107	45	198
Undesired Behaviour	122	60	31	213
TOTAL	386	584	396	

Table A2: Movies and Constructs

Constructs	Sub themes	Frequencies	Total
Physical Constructs	Overloaded Classroom	17	37
	Large Classroom	10	
	Normal Size Classroom	7	
Instructional Constructs	Motivation	35	80
	Planning	23	
	Evaluation	10	
	Time management	7	
	Feedback	5	
Human-based Constructs	Parental pressure	19	74
	Student personality	17	
	Administrative pressure	16	
	Parental ignorance	13	
	Teacher quality	9	
Lesson Planning	Warming up	44	105
	Motivation	39	
	Assessment and Evaluation	16	
	Presentation	3	
	Revision	3	
Communication in Class	Teacher-student	35	86
	Student-student	29	
	Meeting	14	
	Knowing students' names	8	
Undesired Behaviour	Breaking the classroom rules	70	96
	Mobbing	19	
	Physical violence	7	